

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE MODELING OF 3D-PRINTED CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER NYLON COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) using fiber-reinforced thermoplastics is a promising technology for producing fiber-reinforced composite parts with complex geometries, offering structural-grade mechanical behavior along with lightweight properties and recyclability. This study investigates the tensile and failure behavior of composites printed using a dual-nozzle FFF system. Short carbon fiber (SCF)-reinforced nylon was combined with continuous carbon fiber (CCF) nylon layers to produce a hybrid configuration. Various CCF stacking sequences of FFF composite laminates were examined to investigate their impact on the overall mechanical behavior. A finite-element progressive failure (PFA) model was developed using a continuum damage approach. This allowed the prediction of the failure mode in SCF/CCF-reinforced FFF composite and capture various failure modes in the hybrid material system, enabling an understanding of the material's failure behavior. The simulation results were validated using experimental tensile testing for various stacking sequences. The proposed computational approach can be used as a predictive design tool for the mechanical behavior of hybrid fiber-reinforced composites fabricated via FFF.

Keywords: Fiber reinforced composites; Additive manufacturing; Continuum damage mechanics; Progressive failure modeling

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced carbon fiber-reinforced composites are increasingly adopted in aerospace and other structural applications for their high specific strength and stiffness [1], [2]. Recent additive manufacturing techniques, such as fused filament fabrication (FFF), now enable the fabrication of hybrid composite laminates that combine continuous carbon fiber (CCF) with a short carbon fiber (SCF) reinforced nylon matrix within a single printed part [3]. In this approach, a thermoplastic matrix filament (commercially known as Onyx, containing dispersed short carbon fibers) is interleaved with layers of continuous carbon fiber, resulting in a multi-material laminate structure [3], [4]. Dual-nozzle 3D printers (e.g., Markforged Mark Two) deposit the SCF/ nylon material and embed CCF in specified layers, allowing tailored fiber orientations and placement throughout the part [3]. This hybrid architecture aims to leverage the ease of printing and the toughness of short-fiber nylon material, while harnessing the high load-carrying capability of continuous fiber reinforcement. The resulting printed laminates can achieve structural-grade performance in lightweight designs, with the continuous fibers bearing primary loads and the short-fiber thermoplastic providing matrix support and geometric complexity.

Although the FFF process offers structural and manufacturing advantages, the mechanical response of such hybrid laminates is governed by the complex interaction of multiple constituents and orientations [5]. The presence of two distinct reinforcing forms (continuous fiber layers vs. short-fiber matrix layers) creates multiple potential damage mechanisms that can interact. In matrix-dominated

regions (the SCF/nylon layers and off-axis plies), the material may experience matrix cracking and fiber–matrix interfacial debonding, whereas in fiber-dominated CCF layers, tensile loading can cause abrupt fiber bundle fracture when their strength is exceeded [1]. At the same time, the weak interfaces between dissimilar layers are susceptible to delamination. Experiments on 3D-printed CCF/SCF laminates under flexural and tensile loading indeed reveal a combination of these failure modes. For instance, Barber et al. observed extensive interlayer cracking (delamination) between printed layers at failure, occurring at both homogeneous SCF–SCF interfaces and at the heterogeneous SCF–CCF boundaries, with the SCF–CCF interfaces showing the most severe splitting [3]. Capturing the location and mechanism by which each of these damage modes initiates is crucial for understanding the progressive failure of the hybrid composite.

The mechanical behavior of 3D-printed hybrid composites is primarily governed by their anisotropic, heterogeneous architecture, which combines continuous fiber-dominated layers with more compliant short fiber-filled thermoplastic regions [6]. A clear understanding of how layer orientation, material morphology, and interface design influence the structure–property relationships in these hybrid laminates is essential for advancing their use in structural applications. Under service loads, these hybrid laminates inevitably accumulate damage in multiple modes – e.g., matrix cracking, fiber fracture, fiber/matrix debonding, and inter-layer delamination – all of which progressively degrade the structure’s stiffness and strength [1]. Furthermore, phenomenological failure theories (e.g., Tsai–Wu, Hashin) have been developed for composites, achieving reasonable predictions of initial failure to some extent. However, these criteria provide only a static snapshot of failure onset and do not describe how damage propagates. As a result, traditional single-mode or empirical failure models often fail to predict the ultimate strength of hybrid composites when multiple damage mechanisms interact. This limitation motivates the use of a progressive failure analysis (PFA) approach that can track damage initiation and propagation across all relevant modes. While recent studies have explored the mechanical performance of such systems experimentally [1], modeling efforts that quantitatively capture progressive damage and failure evolution in these multi-material, printed architectures remain limited. Existing modeling efforts often rely on simplified elastic assumptions or empirical failure criteria [7], [8], [9], which limits their ability to capture the progressive damage processes that emerge in layered hybrid architectures. More advanced approaches incorporating cohesive zone modeling and continuum damage mechanics (CDMs) have been proposed for conventionally manufactured composites [1], [10], [11], but their extension to printed hybrid composites remains scarce. This study addresses that gap by presenting a progressive failure framework that applies CDMs to simulate multi-mode failure evolution in 3D-printed CF–SCF laminates with varying stacking sequences.

In this study, a finite element-based PFA framework was developed to predict the failure behavior of a hybrid 3D-printed composite laminate reinforced with both short and continuous carbon fibers. The framework incorporates a CDM model for individual plies, featuring cohesive zone elements between layers to simulate interfacial interactions. The hybrid architecture, comprising layers of unidirectional continuous fibers and $\pm 45^\circ$ short fiber-reinforced plies, introduces complex failure interactions due to differences in fiber length, orientation, and reinforcement scale. The CDM-based approach enables a unified simulation of interacting failure modes. The model emphasizes the role of anisotropic material behavior introduced by the layered deposition process and varying fiber orientations. By tracking damage initiation and evolution at the ply level, the framework captures the onset and progression of failure, providing insights into the underlying failure mechanisms. This CDM-based PFA framework demonstrates its effectiveness in predicting the stress–strain response and failure mode of hybrid printed composites, supporting its applicability for performance-driven virtual testing of additively manufactured composite structures.

2 MATERIAL AND PROCESSING

The composite system investigated in this study consists of a dual-material configuration: a SCF reinforced nylon filament, known commercially as Onyx, and nylon reinforced with CCF. Onyx contained ~30% by weight and serves as the semi-structural material matrix. Though it contains discontinuous carbon fibers for enhanced stiffness and strength, the primary reinforcement is derived from CCF layers.

Fabrication was carried out using a Markforged Mark Two 3D printer, which utilizes FFF. The printer has two independent nozzles integrated into a shared print head, one dedicated to extruding the Onyx matrix and the other to laying CCF along predefined paths. During printing, the Onyx filament is heated and deposited layer by layer to form the structural base. CCF tows are then embedded within specific layers at programmed orientations to reinforce the part. The higher temperature of the extruded Onyx results in localized reheating of the underlying layers, promoting interlayer adhesion.

Dog-bone specimens were designed in Autodesk Inventor, sliced in Eiger.io, and fabricated using a hybrid 3D printing process with Onyx as the matrix material and CCF as reinforcement. Each specimen consists of six embedded CCF layers arranged in one of the following configurations: $[0]_6$, $[90]_6$, $[0/90/0]_6$, and $[60/120/0]_6$. The CCF layers are separated by two-layer SCF interleaf regions with a $[+45/-45]$ raster orientation, which serve to enhance interlaminar bonding and enable more effective load transfer between plies. Additionally, the top and bottom surfaces of the specimen consist of four SCF layers, $[+45/-45]_2$, providing structural symmetry and improved surface quality. This architecture yields a multilayered composite with a hierarchical structure that promotes damage dispersion and load redistribution, as further analyzed. The stacking configurations and print orientations of the tested specimens are summarized in Table 1. Fig. 1 illustrates the composite architecture and internal structure. A schematic of the laminate illustrates the stacked configuration of CCF and SCF layers, while microscopic imaging of a representative sample reveals the layered morphology and typical porosity features throughout the laminate. The magnified image of the SCF interleaf reveals void clustering along raster boundaries—features that may impact interfacial strength.

Drying was performed in a closed oven at 70 °C (below the glass transition temperature of nylon), with samples covered in release film to prevent sticking. Moisture removal from the nylon matrix improves stress distribution and increases mechanical strength by mitigating plasticization effects.

Fig. 1 (a) Geometry and layered architecture of the 3D-printed composite specimen. (b) Cross-sectional microstructure

Table 1. Layered Architecture of Hybrid CCF and SCF Laminates

Sample ID	CCF Orientation	SCF Orientation	SCF Layering Structure
S1	$[0]_6$	$[+45/-45]$	2 SCF layers between CCFs; outer SCF layers: $[+45/-45]_2$
S2	$[90]_6$	$[+45/-45]$	Same as above
S3	$[0/90/0]_s$	$[+45/-45]$	Same as above
S4	$[60/120/0]_s$	$[+45/-45]$	Same as above

3 EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION METHODS

3.1 Mechanical Testing

Tensile testing of dog-bone samples was conducted using an MTS Systems. The samples were tested

with a crosshead rate at 1 mm/min until failure occurred. The MTS machine used for tensile testing is equipped with TestWorks4 software. Tensile tests were conducted on each sample with different layer print orientations. After the failure, the stress-strain curves are obtained from each test run.

3.2 SEM Analysis

Microscopic analysis, using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), was employed to investigate the fracture surface morphology of the post-mortem tensile samples. Representative sections of each sample type were used for microstructural analysis. Before imaging, the samples were sputter-coated with a thin layer of Au to enhance surface conductivity and image quality under the SEM. High-resolution SEM images were acquired to examine fracture surfaces and identify failure mechanisms.

4 MODELING PROCEDURE

A finite element analysis (FEA) was used to simulate the tensile behavior of 3D-printed samples. FEA simulation was performed using the Abaqus Implicit commercial software. The model accounted for the material with the printed stacking of SCF and CCF reinforcement. Finite element domains were assigned coordinate systems for every printed layer with a specified material orientation to represent the orientation during printing. CDM was used to model the homogenized material behavior of SCF and CCF layers, assuming transverse isotropy. Cohesive interfaces were implemented to model interactions between the layers by defining the bonding behavior.

4.1 Virtual Sample Modeling Generation

A custom Python-based script was developed and integrated with Abaqus to automate the generation of FEA models for 3D-printed composites. A virtual specimen of 3D printed material is modeled as a continuum in (x, y, z) space (Fig. 2). The stacking structure is generated with specified stacking sequences, ply orientations, thicknesses, material properties, mesh configurations, and cohesive interfaces. The geometry of the laminated composite was defined based on user inputs for the number of stackings, ply orientations, and thicknesses. Each layer was meshed with assigned element orientations using a discrete field. The meshing resolution was controlled using input parameters for element size, allowing accurate modeling of the laminated structure. Sub-domains were assigned local coordinate systems (1,2) to represent individual stacking orientation (Fig 2b). Cohesive interfaces were implemented between each layer to simulate interlaminar bonding. Traction-separation laws were assigned to model the interaction and failure behavior at the interfaces. Cohesive tie constraints were defined to link the cohesive layers with adjacent plies, enabling the simulation of delamination and interfacial failure under tensile loading. Boundary conditions were applied to replicate tensile testing, including displacement and fixed constraints. CDM was implemented to capture progressive damage and failure behavior in the plies.

Figure 2 a. Generated morphology of virtual 3D printed sample b. The orientation of the stacking

4.2 Constitutive Properties and Damage Modeling for Bundles

A continuum damage model was employed to describe the failure modes in the longitudinal and transverse planes of the 3D-printed materials. A user material (UMAT) FORTRAN subroutine for Abaqus standard implicit was used to simulate the damage initiation and propagation in the printing direction and transverse plane. The longitudinal damage, d_1 , considers stiffness degradation in the direction of the freeze-casting, while the transverse damage index, d_2 , reflects the degradation of the material stiffness in the transverse direction to the printing direction. The material constitutive relationship followed the transversely isotropic behavior, as shown in Eq. 1.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{12} \\ \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{23} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{33} \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where C_{ij} is the damaged stiffness matrix depending on the undamaged stiffness components (C_{ij}^0) and damage variables in principal directions (d_i). The damage stiffness components were defined by Eq. 2.

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11} &= (1 - d_1)C_{11}^0; C_{12} = (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)C_{12}^0; \\ C_{13} &= (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)C_{13}^0; C_{22} = (1 - d_2)C_{22}^0; \\ C_{23} &= (1 - d_2)C_{23}^0; C_{33} = (1 - d_2)C_{33}^0; C_{44} = (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)C_{44}^0; \\ C_{55} &= (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)C_{55}^0; C_{66} = (1 - d_2)C_{66}^0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Eq. 3 shows the damage initiation criteria, f_1 , in the printing direction when the corresponding criterion reaches one. Hill's anisotropic failure criterion, f_2 , was used to define the damage initiation in the transverse plane (Eq. 4).

$$f_1 = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{11}^2}{\sigma_{11}^{f,t} \sigma_{11}^{f,c}} + \sigma_{11} \times \left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{11}^{f,t}} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{11}^{f,c}} \right)} \quad (3)$$

$$f_2 = \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{\sigma_{22}^{f,c^2}} - \frac{1}{2\sigma_{11}^{f,c^2}} \right) (\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + \frac{1}{\sigma_{23}^2} \sigma_{23}^2} \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_{ii}^{f,t}$ and $\sigma_{ii}^{f,c}$ are the failure stresses in the principal directions in tension and compression, respectively. The damage variables (d_1 and d_2), evolves from 0 to 1, where 0 represents the undamaged material, and one corresponds to the fully damaged state (E. 5).

$$d_i = 1 - \frac{\sigma_{ii}^f}{C_{ii}f_i} \exp\left(\frac{\sigma_{ii}^f(\sigma_{ii}^f/C_{ii} - f_i)l^*}{G_c}\right), i = 1,2 \quad (5)$$

where, l^* is the characteristic element length associated with the material and G_c is the fracture energy in the lamellar direction. Material constitutive properties for CCF and SCF stacking are represented in Tables 2-3 and are derived using micromechanical models as described in Appendix A.1 and A.2. The assigned transverse tensile strength for the CCF layers reflects the influence of the ductile SCF matrix in which the continuous carbon fibers are embedded. While this value is higher than typical for thermoset-based unidirectional laminates, it is consistent with prior observations in layered

discontinuous fiber composite (LDFC) systems, where matrix ductility and constrained damage propagation contribute to enhanced transverse performance [12], [13].

Table 2. Stiffness and strength properties for 3D printed CCF layers

Material property	Value
Longitudinal modulus, E_{11} (MPa)	60,000
Transverse modulus, E_{22}, E_{33} (MPa)	5,000
Shear modulus, G_{12}, G_{13} (MPa)	3,000
Shear modulus, G_{23} (MPa)	1,000
Poisson's ratios, ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.29
Longitudinal tensile strength, F_{1t} (MPa)	100
Transverse tensile strength, F_{2t} (MPa)	200
Fracture energy G_c [kJ/m ²]	8

Table 3. Stiffness and strength properties for 3D printed SCF layers

Material property	Value
Longitudinal modulus, E_{11} (MPa)	5,000
Transverse modulus, E_{22}, E_{33} (MPa)	1,800
Shear modulus, G_{12}, G_{13} (MPa)	2,000
Shear modulus, G_{23} (MPa)	690
Poisson's ratios, ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.38
Longitudinal tensile strength, F_{1t} (MPa)	100
Transverse tensile strength, F_{2t} (MPa)	50
Fracture energy G_c [kJ/m ²]	4

The CDM with transversely isotropic damage for 3D printed stacking combined with a cohesive zone modeling (CZM) at the interfaces between printed stacking to capture debonding using a traction separation law. Eq. 6 shows the constitutive equation of traction separation, where interlaminar σ_{ij} stress, δ_j is the relative separation between the elements, d is the damage variable, and $k_i^0 = 730 \times 10^6$ MPa/mm is the initial stiffness.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (1-d)k_1^0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & (1-d)k_2^0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-d)k_3^0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta_1 \\ \delta_2 \\ \delta_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The failure initiation criterion of the delamination between the printed layers is given by Eq. 7 where $N_{max} = 40$ MPa and $S_{max} = T_{max} = 60$ MPa represent the normal and shear cohesive strengths, respectively.

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{N_{max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{max}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{T_{max}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (7)$$

The propagation of the delamination is defined by a linear fracture mechanism of power law through Eq. 8 [14].

$$\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}} + \frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}} + \frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIC}} = 1 \quad (8)$$

where G_I, G_{II}, G_{III} are the work done by the tractions and their corresponding displacements in the normal and shear directions, and $G_{IC}, G_{IIC}, G_{IIIC}$ are the critical strain energy release rates corresponding to the fracture modes, where $G_{IC} = 1 \text{ kJ/m}^2, G_{IIC} = G_{IIIC} = 2 \text{ kJ/m}^2$.

5 NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

5.1 Comparison of Experimental and Numerical Modeling Predictions

Figure 3 shows the stress–strain behavior of 3D-printed composite laminates consisting of CCF/LCF layers. Four different CCF stacking sequences, [0], [0/90/0], [60/120/0], and [90], are examined under uniaxial tensile loading, with both experimental results and simulation data presented for comparison. Figure 4 compares the average UTS of hybrid 3D-printed laminates. Experimental results are shown with error bars representing standard deviation, while red markers indicate predictions from simulations. The [0] CCF laminate exhibits the highest stiffness and strength, as the fiber alignment is parallel to the loading direction, and the $\pm 45^\circ$ SCF layers provide additional shear resistance without significantly compromising axial load transfer. The [90] CCF laminate, with fibers oriented transverse to the loading direction, exhibits the lowest tensile strength and stiffness, as the load is primarily borne by the $\pm 45^\circ$ SCF layers, which have lower axial modulus compared to the CCF interlayers. The [0/90/0]_s and [60/120/0]_s laminates demonstrate intermediate strengths, governed by the presence of off-axis CCF layers that reduce axial stiffness, while the alternating $\pm 45^\circ$ SCF layers enhance damage tolerance and redistribute local stress. The simulation results, based on continuum damage mechanics, align well with the experimental data, capturing the variation in stiffness, peak strength, and strain at failure across stacking sequences. These findings confirm the role of CCF layup design and the synergy between reinforcement and matrix orientations in determining the strength of additively manufactured composite laminates.

Figure 3. Stress–strain curves from experimental tests and finite element simulations for hybrid 3D-printed polymer composite laminates with different CCF stacking

Figure 4. Comparison of experimental and simulation results for the ultimate tensile strength of hybrid 3D-printed polymer composite laminates with different CCF stacking.

5.2 Damage Propagation

Failure in the hybrid 3D-printed polymer composite laminate arises from the complex interplay of multiple damage mechanisms, including fiber/matrix debonding, matrix cracking, interstacking delamination, and fiber pull-out. The damage is spatially distributed throughout the composite volume, reflecting the heterogeneous nature of the printed architecture and interfaces. Initiation and propagation occur concurrently at multiple sites, driven by the tailored stacking sequence and directional deposition of both continuous and short fibers. This architecture introduces intrinsic structural redundancy, allowing for local load redistribution after damage initiates. As a result, the laminate exhibits multi-site failure behavior.

The fracture surfaces observed in the SEM images (Fig 5) reveal mix-mode failure mechanisms within the 3D-printed composite laminate composed of CCF and SCF matrix stacking. Figures a. and b. shows the fracture surface of $[0]_6$ CCF stacking sample (200 \times) and highlights failure in the continuous fiber region, where long, aligned fibers exhibit pull-out and interfacial debonding. This suggests that failure was dominated by fiber–matrix interface separation. Fig. 5b (350 \times) shows the fracture surface of the SCF stacking region, characterized by a rough short fiber pull-out and matrix cracking.

Figures c. and d. shows the fracture surface of $[90]_6$ CCF stacking sample. Long-aligned fibers protrude from the matrix, indicating a dominant fiber pull-out mechanism. The gaps between the matrix and fibers suggest interfacial debonding between the CF and the surrounding polymer. Figure d shows the visible gaps between the stacking point and interlaminar delamination and interstacking shearing. Figures e. and f. show the fracture surface of $[60/120/0]_5$ CCF stacking sample. Figure F's upper stacking displays SCF stacking with rough, polymer-rich morphology, randomly oriented broken fibers, and matrix cracking. The central region includes a distinct, aligned bundle of CF, indicating fiber pullout and matrix fiber debonding.

Figure 5. SEM images of fracture surfaces in hybrid 3D-printed polymer composite laminates with continuous carbon fiber (CCF) interstacking: (a) and (b) correspond to the $[0]_6$ stacking, (c) and (d) to the $[90]_6$ stacking, and (e) and (f) to the $[60/120/0]_5$ stacking configuration.

Figure 6 illustrates the cumulative relative frequency distributions of the damage variables in the simulations. The figure highlights distinct damage indices in the fiber direction (d_1) and the transverse direction (d_2), revealing the directionality and progression of failure at peak stress. The 0° CCF stacking exhibits concentrated and localized damage in the fiber direction (d_1), which can be attributed to the fiber breakage under axial tensile loading. This confirms that the stacking is the primary load-bearing component, effectively resisting tensile stress until failure initiation. Transverse damage (d_2) in these stackings remains limited and confined, suggesting strong out-of-plane stability and minimal matrix cracking attributed to the alignment and stiffness of the continuous fibers. In contrast, this configuration's SCF stacking displays more widespread and diffused damage patterns. The d_1 field in the SCF stacking shows scattered failure. The d_2 damage in these regions is more prominent and spatially extended, indicating matrix-dominated transverse cracking and reduced out-of-plane resistance.

In the $[90]_6$ CCF sample, the layers are oriented perpendicular to the loading direction, resulting in negligible or delayed fiber-aligned damage. Consequently, they do not significantly contribute to axial load bearing. Instead, transverse damage becomes dominant, manifesting as matrix cracking. The simulation results also show the dominant d_2 damage for CCF and SCF stacking.

The $[0/90/0]_5$ interstacking CCF laminate, the 90° CCF, and the SCF stacking dominate the transverse damage (d_2) field. This pattern reflects the matrix-dominated failure behavior of the 90° plies, which contribute minimally to axial strength. The SCF stacking further exhibits extensive transverse matrix cracking due to shear-induced stresses. In the $[60/120/0]_5$ CCF laminate, the d_2 field shows localized transverse damage in the 60° and 120° CCF stacking. The SCF stacking exhibits widespread

transverse damage, as seen in extended matrix cracking and interfacial failure under combined transverse and shear loading.

Figure 6. This is an example of a figure. FE simulation results showing fiber-direction (d_1) and transverse (d_2) damage distributions in 3D-printed laminates with various CCF stacking configurations

6 CONCLUSIONS

This study developed and validated a progressive failure modeling framework for 3D-printed hybrid composite laminates composed of CCF and SCF-nylon to predict mechanical behavior and failure evolution. Various stacking sequences were fabricated to investigate the influence of fiber orientation and hybrid architecture on mechanical performance. The finite element model, based on CDM, captured intralaminar damage mechanisms, such as fiber fracture and matrix cracking, as well as interlaminar delamination through cohesive interface modeling. The model showed close agreement with experimental tensile results, not only in terms of ultimate tensile strength and stiffness but also in spatial damage distribution, except for the [0]^o CCF configuration, where the prediction underestimates the strength due to limitations in calibrating the longitudinal tensile strength and fiber-dominated failure parameters. Results revealed that stacking configurations with off-axis CCF layers and SCF interleaves led to higher accumulation of transverse and shear-driven damage, while unidirectional fiber alignments promoted fiber-dominated failure. While further calibration of principal material properties is warranted, this modeling framework enables the predictive analysis of printed composites with variable fiber orientations and material interactions, supporting virtual design optimization in advanced engineering applications.

APPENDIX A

A.1 Constitutive Properties of CCF

The printed CCF stackings are modeled as a unidirectional composite of continuous carbon fibers embedded in the SCF matrix. The fibers are assumed to be perfectly aligned in the 1-direction (longitudinal), and the composite is treated as anisotropic.

The fiber volume fraction is $V_f = 0.4$. The constituent properties used in the calculations are:

- Carbon fiber: $E_f = 190$ GPa, $G_f = 20$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.2$

- SCF matrix: $E_m = 1.8$ GPa, $G_m = 0.7$ GPa, $\nu_m = 0.42$

Longitudinal modulus (E_{11}) is calculated using the Rule of Mixtures:

$$E_{11} = V_f \times E_f + (1 - V_f) \times E_m \quad (\text{A-1})$$

To account for imperfections and practical limitations, a conservative value of $E_{11} = 60,000$ MPa is assigned.

Transverse modulus ($E_{22} = E_{33}$) is estimated using the Inverse Rule of Mixtures:

$$1/E_{22} = V_f/E_f + (1 - V_f)/E_m \quad (\text{A-2})$$

Shear moduli ($G_{12} = G_{13}$):

$$1/G_{12} = V_f/G_f + (1 - V_f)/G_m \quad (\text{A-3})$$

Transverse shear modulus (G_{23}) is matrix-dominated: $G_{23} \approx G_m = 1,000$ MPa

Poisson's Ratios:

$$\nu_{12} = V_f \times \nu_f + (1 - V_f) \times \nu_m \quad (\text{A-4})$$

$\nu_{13} = \nu_{12}$ (assumed symmetry)

Longitudinal tensile strength (F_{1t}):

$$F_{1t} = V_f \times \sigma_f + (1 - V_f) \times \sigma_m \quad (\text{A-5})$$

($\sigma_f = 2000$ MPa, $\sigma_m = 80$ MPa)

A.1 Constitutive Properties of SCF Layers

Fibers in these layers are assumed to be partially aligned due to the extrusion process, and the resulting material is treated as anisotropic.

The effective elastic modulus is calculated using the Halpin–Tsai equation:

$$E_c = E_m \times [(1 + \xi \times \eta \times V_f)/(1 - \eta \times V_f)] \quad (\text{A-6})$$

where

$$\eta = (\frac{E_f}{E_m} - 1)/(\frac{E_f}{E_m} + \xi) \quad (\text{A-7})$$

($\xi = 2$)

Tensile strength is estimated using a modified Rule of Mixtures:

$$\sigma_c = \eta_0 \times \beta \times V_f \times \sigma_f + (1 - V_f) \times \sigma_m \quad (\text{A-8})$$

$\eta_0 = 0.4$ (orientation efficiency), $\beta = 0.6$ (length efficiency)

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